

Synthesis of 2-Sulfanilamido Thiazole Derivatives and Their Antibacterial Activity

D B INGLE* M S SHINGARE and V. H PATIL

Department of Chemistry Marathwada University, Aurangabad 431002

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Some 2-amino-4-(disubstituted phenyl)-5-methyl thiazoles were synthesised and then converted to a number of sulfanilamido derivatives. The title compounds were tested for antibacterial activity.

THE thiazole analogues of sulfapyridine were earlier prepared and tested for chemotherapeutic activity^{1, 2}. Desai *et al*³ reported the synthesis of a series of N-heterocyclic substituted sulfonamides and found that 4-amino-N-(4, 5-dimethyl-2-thiazolyl)-1-naphthalene sulfonamide was the most active of all other thiazole derivatives against *S aureus* and *S coli*. 4-Amino-N-(5-methyl-2-thiazolyl)- and 4-amino-4-(4, 5-dimethyl-2-thiazolyl)-benzene sulfonamides were also found to be active against bacterial infection⁴. We report herein the synthesis of some 2-amino-4-(2-methoxy-3/5 substituted phenyl)-5-methyl thiazoles and their sulfanilamido derivatives, with chloro and methyl substituents and their screening for antibacterial activities.

The *o*-methoxy propiophenones required as the starting material were obtained by the Fries migration of substituted propiophenones and methylation of the *o*-hydroxy propiophenones. The 2-amino thiazoles were prepared⁵ by the condensation of substituted propiophenones with thiourea in presence of iodine. These 2-amino-4-(substituted phenyl)-5-

methyl thiazoles (Table 1) were then treated with *p*-substituted benzene sulfonyl chlorides to get 2-sulfanilamido thiazole derivatives. The compounds containing acetamido group were hydrolysed to give the corresponding amino compounds.

The IR spectra of 2-amino-4-(substituted phenyl)-5-methyl thiazole showed absorption in the range of 3120 to 3480 cm⁻¹ with higher intensity and at 1610 to 1645 cm⁻¹ due to N-H stretching and bending vibrations respectively. The thiazole nucleus had characteristic absorption at around 1530, 1400, 1380, 1020, 800 cm⁻¹. The respective asymmetric and symmetric stretching modes of vibration of S=O from sulfanilamido group appeared in the range of 1380 to 1335 and 1170 to 1160 cm⁻¹.

Experimental

Synthesis of 2-amino-4-(substituted phenyl)-5-methyl thiazoles (I). A mixture of substituted propiophenone (0.1 mol), thiourea (0.25 mol, 19 g) and iodine (0.1 mol, 25.4 g) was heated on water-bath for 26 hr. The 2-amino-4-(substituted phenyl)-5-methyl thiazole was isolated following the method

TABLE 1 2-AMINO 4-(SUBSTITUTED PHENYL) 5 METHYL THIAZOLES

Compd no	M p °C	Yield %	Mol formula	Elemental analysis			
				Found		Requires	
				C%	H%	C%	H%
Ia	204	64	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ ON ₂ SCl	51.54	4.00	51.96	4.33
Ib	146	75	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ ON ₂ SCl	51.61	4.21	51.96	4.33
Ic	194	71	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ ON ₂ S	61.05	5.51	61.53	5.98

TABLE 2 2-SULFANILAMIDO 4 (SUBSTITUTED PHENYL) 5-METHYL THIAZOLES

Compd no	M p °C	Yield %	Mol formula	% S	
				Found	Requires
IIa	130	85	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₂ S ₂ Cl	15.21	15.68
IIb	169	85	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₂ S ₂ Cl	15.32	15.68
IIc	188.9	64	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₂ S ₂	16.51	16.49
IId	257	59	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₂ S ₂ ClBr	13.00	13.14
IIe	171	57	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₂ S ₂ ClBr	13.20	13.24
IIf	145	59	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₂ S ₂ Cl	16.10	15.80
IIg	105	69	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₂ S ₂ Cl	13.92	14.19
IIh	162	77	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₄ N ₂ S ₂ Cl	13.89	14.19
IIi	338	78	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ O ₄ N ₂ S ₂	14.60	14.84
IIj	84	68	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₂ S ₂ Cl	15.51	15.69
IIk	150	78	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₂ S ₂ Cl	15.15	15.69
III	298	79	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₂ S ₂	16.10	16.45

* For correspondence

of Dodson and King⁵ and crystallised from ethanol. The data are given in Table 1.

- I a $R_1 = \text{Cl}, R_2 = \text{H}$
 b $R_1 = \text{H}, R_2 = \text{Cl}$
 c $R_1 = \text{H}, R_2 = \text{CH}_3$
- II a $R_1 = \text{Cl}, R_2 = \text{H}, R_3 = \text{CH}_3$
 b $R_1 = \text{H}, R_2 = \text{Cl}, R_3 = \text{CH}_3$
 c $R_1 = \text{H}, R_2 = \text{CH}_3, R_3 = \text{CH}_3$
 d $R_1 = \text{Cl}, R_2 = \text{H}, R_3 = \text{Br}$
 e $R_1 = \text{H}, R_2 = \text{Cl}, R_3 = \text{Br}$
 f $R_1 = \text{H}, R_2 = \text{CH}_3, R_3 = \text{Cl}$
 g $R_1 = \text{Cl}, R_2 = \text{H}, R_3 = \text{NHCOCH}_3$
 h $R_1 = \text{H}, R_2 = \text{Cl}, R_3 = \text{NHCOCH}_3$
 i $R_1 = \text{H}, R_2 = \text{CH}_3, R_3 = \text{NHCOCH}_3$
 j $R_1 = \text{Cl}, R_2 = \text{H}, R_3 = \text{NH}_2$
 k $R_1 = \text{H}, R_2 = \text{Cl}, R_3 = \text{NH}_2$
 l $R_1 = \text{H}, R_2 = \text{CH}_3, R_3 = \text{NH}_2$

General procedure for the synthesis of 2-sulfanilamido-4-(substituted-phenyl)-5-methyl thiazoles (II)
 A mixture of 2-amino-4-(substituted phenyl)-5-methyl thiazole (0.1 mol), *p*-substituted benzene sulfonyl chloride (0.11 mol) and dry pyridine (20 ml) was heated on water-bath for one hr and kept at room temp. for 48 hr. The reaction mixture was poured on to ice containing a little conc. H_2SO_4 with stirring. The crude product obtained was washed with dil. NaHCO_3 solution and finally

with distilled water. It was crystallised from aq. ethanol. Methyl-, bromo-, chloro-, and acetamido-benzene sulfonyl chlorides were condensed with different 2-amino thiazoles to give 2-sulfanilamido-4-(substituted phenyl)-5-methyl thiazoles. The 2-(4'-acetamido sulfanilamido)-4-(substituted phenyl)-5-methyl thiazole derivatives were hydrolysed by 30% alc HCl to 2-sulfanilamido-4-(substituted phenyl)-5-methyl thiazoles which were also crystallised from aq. ethanol. The data are given in Table 2.

Activity

All the 2-sulfanilamido thiazoles were tested against four different organisms, viz. *V comma*, *M tuberculosis*, *S aureus* and *S typhi*. In general, the compounds are active against *M tuberculosis*. 2-Sulfanilamido-4-(2'-methoxy-3-chlorophenyl)-5-methyl thiazole (IIj) was found to be the most active and its activity is quite comparable to that of streptomycin ($\text{H}_{37} \text{Rv/strain}$).

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